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Incidence of Squamous Cell Carcinoma in Hairless Mice Irradiated with Ultraviolet Light in Relation to Intake of Ascorbic Acid (Vitamin C) and of D, L- α -Tocopheryl Acetate (Vitamin E)

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Summary: We have carried out a study of large malignant skin tumors (squamous-cell carcinomas) and other lesions in "hairless" mice (in groups of 45 or 60 mice) intermittently exposed to ultraviolet light over a period of 15 weeks, beginning when the mice were about 8 weeks old. Various groups were given a standard diet (Wayne Lab-Blox) or the same food with added vitamin C or vitamin E throughout the study. Lesions, classified by histopathologic study as atypical squamous-cell proliferations varying from early actinic keratoses to invasive poorly differentiated squamous-cell carcinomas, had begun to develop by the end of the period of irradiation. They were counted twice a month for five months. The observed fraction of mice that developed lesions during successive time periods was analyzed by the statistical method recommended by a committee of the International Agency for Research on Cancer. A pronounced effect of vitamin C in decreasing the incidence of the malignant lesions was observed with very high statistical significance. No significant effect of vitamin E was observed. We conclude that vitamin C should be given especial attention with respect to the relation between diet and cancer.

There has been much interest in vitamin C and other dietary factors in relation to the incidence of and mortality from cancer in human beings, stimulated especially by the studies of the value of vitamin C for patients with advanced cancer in Vale of Leven Hospital, Loch Lomondside, Scotland, from 1971 on (1-10). The suggestion was made to us in 1973 by officers of the National Cancer Institute [9] that we carry on studies of cancer in animals in relation to vitamin C. We had also been interested in the possible value of other nutrients in helping to control cancer. We were able to

begin these studies in 1976, and we report in this paper some of the results of four investigations, all involving "hairless" mice exposed to ultraviolet light in a standard way.

The work of BLACK with hairless mice was brought to the attention of one of us (L. P.) by Professor DOLE. BLACK and his collaborators had reported that cholesterol-5 α , 6 α -epoxide (cholestan-5 α , 6 α -epoxy-3 β -ol), a carcinogenic sterol, is formed in skin on ultraviolet irradiation, both in humans [11] and in mice [12, 13], and they also reported suppression by dietary antioxidants of tumor formation induced in hairless mice by exposure to ultraviolet light [12]. We are grateful to Dr. BLACK for having given us much information and advice about his techniques, which we have essentially duplicated in our work, and for having encouraged us to carry out the studies reported in this paper.

Materials and Methods

The "hairless" mouse is a mutant that loses its hair at about three weeks after birth. It does not have the thymus defect that the nude mutant has. Our mice, females, 6 to 9 weeks old, were of the SKh-hr strain and were obtained from Temple University Health Sciences Center, Philadelphia, Pennsylvania, in four batches, one batch at the beginning of each of our experiments: Experiment I, January 1976; II, February 1977; III, November 1977, and A, January 1980. Irradiation began two or three weeks after receipt of the mice, after they had been on the special diets for about 10 days, and was continued, with daily exposures (5 days per week), for about 15 weeks, the total exposure being 135 J cm⁻². The irradiation was made with GE-UA3 mercury arc lamps, as described by BLACK, except that an automatic timing device was added. About every two weeks the daily exposure level was increased by small increments from the initial value 1.13 J cm⁻² to the final value 1.97 J cm⁻² (checked occasionally) to compensate for epidermal thickening [12]. No erythema was noted. The mice were observed through a window during irradiation and it was verified that they all received full dorsal exposure - they did not pile on top of one another. Readings of lesions were made every 14 days, beginning two weeks before the end of the period of irradiation.

The diets used in this study are described in Table I. The diets, based on Wayne Lab-Blox mash ("chow") purchased from James Grain Co., San Jose, were usually prepared in 4-kg batches. The Lab-Blox mash was mixed with the other substances and blended for about 5 min in a Patterson-Kelley Twin Shell Blender, Model LB-S-8. Water was then added (Table I) and the blending was continued for 5 min. The food was then pelleted in a California Pellet Mill (Type 3) with a 1/2-inch die and fan-dried at room temperature. It was then placed in 1-gallon jars, sealed, and frozen at -40°C until needed. It was warmed to room temperature before it was placed in the cages. L-Ascorbic acid and sodium L-ascorbate were purchased from Bronson Pharmaceuticals, La Canada, California, and D, L- α -tocopheryl acetate was donated by

Hoffmann-La Roche, Inc. The measured pH of a slurry (11 g of ground pellets plus 50 ml of water) was 4.6 for 4.8% ascorbic acid and 4.3 for 9.2%. The amounts of food eaten by the mice were not measured; we observed, however, that approximately the same amounts were eaten by mice of all groups except those of III d (chow plus 19.2% vitamin C), which ate a somewhat smaller amount.

The nature of the lesions

Sixty of the lesions were subjected to histopathologic study by three pathologists, who agreed with one another and with BLACK in classifying them as atypical squamous-cell proliferations varying from early actinic keratoses to invasive poorly-differentiated squamous-cell carcinomas. The small lesions (up to 2 mm in diameter) were mostly actinic keratoses, and the larger lesions (6 mm or more in diameter) were squamous-cell carcinomas, some ulcerated, occasionally with foci of highly anaplastic or undifferentiated cells, and some showing intense mitotic activity, while other lesions consisted of relatively well-differentiated keratin-producing cells. The lesions of intermediate size mainly represented either hypertrophic actinic keratoses or low grade squamous-cell carcinomas. There were a few flat, stellate ulcers that appeared grossly different from the other lesions and that were found on microscopic examination to consist of bizarre spindle-cells; they were considered to represent a pseudosarcomatous variety of squamous-cell carcinoma.

In addition, in the 8th, 9th, and 10th readings of Experiment II and in all readings of Experiment III every lesion was classified by visual inspection by one of us (R. W.) as an actinic keratosis, a papilloma, or a carcinoma. This classification was checked for 59 of the lesions by comparison with the independent classification of the same lesions by two pathologists. Of the 38 lesions classified by visual inspections as malignant ulcers or carcinomas, 36 were classified, in a blind check, as carcinomas by the first pathologist and all 38 by the second. These lesions were mainly large, 4 mm or more in diameter. Of the 21 smaller lesions, designated as actinic keratoses or papillomas, 3 were classified as carcinomas and 18 as non-malignant dyskeratoses by the first pathologist and 16 as carcinomas and 5 as non-malignant by the second pathologist.

Table II shows the results of R. W.'s classification.

The development of the malignant lesions

In each experiment there were several groups of mice, receiving different diets, with the number of mice in a group between 45 and 60 (9 to 12 cages, with 5 mice per cage). We report here on four groups run simultaneously in 1976 (Experiment I), 11 in 1977 (Experiment II), 4 in 1978 (Experiment III), and 2 in 1980 (Experiment A). The mice were inspected and weighed every 14 days. The lesion on each mouse in five cat-

egories (0 to 1.9 mm in diameter, 2 to 3.9, 4 to 5.9, 6 to 9.9, and 10 mm or more) were counted and recorded. The lesions were classified by visual inspection as actinic keratoses, papillomas, and carcinomas, as discussed above.

In Tables III, IV, V, and IX we show for each group of mice in Experiments II, III (C), III (E), and A the number of mice in the group and the number with any lesions at each of 10 readings, the number with lesions 2 mm or more, 4 mm or more, 6 mm or more, and 10 mm or more in diameter. The diameter was taken as the average of the largest and smallest diameters parallel to the surface of the skin, as measured with a millimeter rule. All measurements and counts were made by the same person (R. W.).

Each group consisted initially of 45 mice, except IIa and IIIa, with 60, and Ab, with 39. In Experiments II and III a few mice died, mostly by accident or unknown cause, in nearly every group, the average number being 3. The number of mice at risk (alive and without lesions of the indicated size) during each time period is given in the tables.

The unirradiated controls

In Experiment III there was also a group of 10 mice receiving Wayne Lab-Blox and the same treatment as the other mice except that they were not irradiated. Three of these mice developed a few very small sebaceous cysts, and a fourth showed one small lesion, possibly a papilloma, which, however, disappeared after two weeks. Accordingly the development of lesions in the other groups can be ascribed with confidence to the radiation that they were exposed to.

The mean weight at the 10th reading of the unirradiated mice was 33.1 (0.7) g. This is larger than the values for all of the Experiment-III irradiated groups, the extra weight being between 1.1 g and 3.5 g. The mean value for the irradiated mice is 30.8 (0.57) g, and the probability that the control group is 2.3 g heavier because of a statistical fluctuation is small, with $P \leq 0.001$. Accordingly, we may conclude that irradiation leads to a lower mean weight for hairless mice that do not develop large lesions than for unirradiated hairless mice, under the conditions of our study.

The statistical treatment

We have analyzed the observations reported in the tables in a number of ways, all with nearly the same conclusions. In Tables III, IV, V, and IX the results are given of the method of statistical analysis recommended to us by R. PETO of the Imperial Cancer Research Fund Department of Cancer Studies, Nuffield Department of Clinical Medicine, Radcliffe Infirmary, Oxford, England, which seems to us also to be the most appropriate one. This method [14] was formulated for the International Agency for Research on Cancer, Lyon, France, by a group of statisticians from England, the United States of America, France, and Germany (R. PETO, R. G. GRAY, S. PARISH,

S. RICHARDS, and J. PETO of Oxford, P. N. Lee of London, M. C. PIKE of the School of Medicine of the University of Southern California, N. E. DAY of the IARC in France, and J. WAHRENDORF of the German Cancer Research Center in Heidelberg). It involves the use of all of the groups of animals in the test of a carcinogenic agent or protective substance and is not based significantly on the assumption of a particular response function. In the procedure a comparison is made of the number of at-risk animals in a group that develop a particular type of tumor with the number that would have been expected had the age-specific tumor-onset rates been the same in all of the groups. The word "expected" means "expected on the basis of the average outcome among all the treatment groups of such animals in the whole experiment" [14]. If the observed number is greater than the expected number in some groups, then it must be less than the expected number in others, for the sum for all groups is exactly the total number for the whole set.

If there appears to be a tendency for the observed numbers to be less than the expected numbers in the groups receiving the higher doses of the protective substance being tested, a significance level (a one-tailed P -value) may be calculated that estimates the probability that a trend as big as or bigger than the observed trend would arise by chance alone.

The authors of the IARC report [14] state that this statistical treatment may be reasonably considered to be the optimum and that it should usually supersede the separate pieces of information arising from statistical comparisons of various pairs of individual groups with each other or judgment of whether a plausible dose-response relationship appears to exist. They also point out that the P -values should not be interpreted in an inflexible way. "A P -value of 0.001 from a well-run experiment is to most people convincing evidence that treatment does affect cancer-onset rates even in the entire absence of any supporting evidence, but a P -value around 0.05 should usually not be, and still less should the interpretation of P -values just above and just below 0.05 differ markedly."

In Tables III, IV, V, and IX a separate calculation is made for each two-weeks interval between readings and for each of the five sizes of lesions. The calculation involves the way in which the fraction of the mice at risk at the beginning of the two-weeks interval that have developed their first lesion of the selected size varies with the amount of vitamin C or vitamin E in the diet. This calculation is made in the following way, taken from the IARC monograph [14]. Let N_i be the number of mice at risk at the beginning of the interval in the i^{th} group of the series with different amounts of the additive to the diet (vitamin C or E); that is, the number without a lesion of the selected size at the beginning of the interval and alive at the end of the interval. $N = \sum N_i$ is the total number of the mice. O_i the number of these mice in the i^{th} group that had developed such a lesion during this interval, $O = \sum O_i$ is their total for the series, and O/N is the average fraction for the whole series of the mice at risk that had developed the first lesion during this interval. We next calculate the number of mice in each group that would be expected to develop a first lesion if the additive had no effect.

The expected number of mice at risk with new lesions in each group is given by the equation

$$E_i = \frac{N_i O}{N} \quad (1)$$

The quantity $O_i - E_i$ is then the difference between the observed and the expected number of mice with new lesions in the i^{th} group.

These quantities $O_i - E_i$ are then weighted by multiplication by the respective dosages of the preventive substance, D_i :

$$A_i = D_i (O_i - E_i) \quad (2)$$

The quantities A , B_i , B , C_i , C , and Q are defined as

$$A = \Sigma A_i \quad (3)$$

$$B_i = D_i E_i \quad (4)$$

$$B = \Sigma B_i \quad (5)$$

$$C_i = D_i^2 E_i = D_i B_i \quad (6)$$

$$C = \Sigma C_i \quad (7)$$

$$Q = C - \frac{B^2}{E} \quad (8)$$

The trend statistic T is then

$$T = A \quad (9)$$

The variance V of the trend statistic is

$$V = \frac{Q(N-E)}{N-1} \quad (10)$$

with $E = \Sigma E_i$.

In the calculation of the significance of a number of readings use is made of other qualities, the trend sum T^* and the variance sum V^* , calculated by the equations

$$T^* = \Sigma T \quad (11)$$

and

$$V^* = \Sigma V \quad (12)$$

In our tables these sums are taken over the series of readings.

The standardized test statistic for trend, Z^* , is

$$Z^* = T^* V^{*-1/2} \quad (13)$$

This quantity varies essentially as a normal distribution, and it represents the number of standard deviations, $V^{*1/2}$, of the observed trend statistic T^* . The value of P (one-tailed) is the area of the normalized normal distribution curve beyond Z^* .

The preliminary study, Experiment I

The preliminary study (Experiment I) was stopped 117 days after the middle of the period of irradiation, as had been done by BLACK. At this time 9% of the mice had died. This high rate may have resulted from our lack of experience in handling the mice. At the 117-day reading the percentages of surviving mice with lesions greater than 4 mm in diameter in four groups, chow, chow plus 1.2% C, chow plus 0.05% E, and chow plus the BLACK mixture of antioxidants, were 24, 27, 29, and 5, respectively. The protective effect for the fourth group was very nearly the same as that reported by BLACK. No significant effect of vitamin C or vitamin E was observed in this preliminary experiment.

The experience gained in Experiment I was of value in the later experiments, which were continued for a longer time with fewer losses of mice.

Experiments II and III: Vitamin C

In Experiments II and III there were initially 45 mice per group (60 for IIa and IIIa). The number alive, the number at risk for lesions of different sizes (those smaller than 2 mm in diameter, 2 mm or larger, 4 mm or larger, 6 mm or larger, and 10 mm or larger) at the beginning of each period, and the number of those at risk that developed one or more lesions during the period are given in Table III for groups IIa to IIf (chow plus 0, 0.3, 0.6, 1.2, 2.4, or 4.8% of added vitamin C) and in Table IV for groups IIIa, IIIb, IIIc, and IIId (chow plus 0 to 19% of added vitamin C). The results of applying the IARC statistical treatment described in a previous section are also given in the tables.

The values for the ten readings in a set are, of course, not completely independent of one another. For 22 early readings of larger lesions in Tables III and IV the trend sums are zero, because no mice in any group had yet developed these lesions. For the other 78 readings the trend sums are all negative. This observation is a clear indication that the addition of vitamin C delays the formation of the lesions. The statistical significance, as indicated by the small values of P [1], is seen to be high.

Of the 78 P -values in Tables III and IV, 29 are equal to or less than 0.001. Inspection of the larger values shows that in general they correspond to sets for which the statistical uncertainty is expected to be great, either because the fraction of mice with lesions is close to zero or because it is close to unity. The fraction is close to zero for the early readings of the largest lesions; for example, in Table IV the fourth and fifth readings for lesions 6 mm or more in diameter and the fifth, sixth, and seventh

readings for lesions 10 mm or more in diameter. In all five cases the value of P is 0.15; and in all five cases there is only one mouse in the total of 190 with lesions of the indicated size (this mouse being in the group with no added vitamin C). The fraction is close to unity for the last readings with all lesions considered, as for reading 10 for the any-lesion count in Table III and readings 9 and 10 in Table IV, all with $P = 0.30$. For this reading in Table III the mice with lesions number 264 of a total of 277, and for the two readings in Table IV they number 176 and 183 of a total of 190. (These small lesions are for the most part not malignant.)

Correspondingly, low values of P are found in the regions where the fraction of mice with lesions is in the middle range. Thus in Table IV the very low value $P \leq 0.00005$ is found for the any-lesion count at readings 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10, for the 2 mm or more count at readings 7, 8, and 9, for the 4 mm or more count at readings 7, 8, 9, and 10, and for the 6 mm or more count at readings 9 and 10.

The values for lesions greater than 4 mm in diameter are of special interest in relation to cancer, because most of these lesions are malignant. Inspection of Tables III and IV shows that the corresponding values of P are very small. We conclude accordingly that the observed decreases in the number of mice with malignant lesions accompanying an increase in the amount of vitamin C in their food is real, and that vitamin C decreases the age-specific incidence of skin cancer caused by irradiation with ultraviolet light in the strain of hairless mice used in our studies.

The observed numbers of lesions of various sizes in the different groups at the ten reading times are given in Tables VI, VII, and VIII. Inspection indicates that these numbers change from group to group and with time in a way that parallels the changes shown in Tables III, IV, and V. We are not communicating the results of a detailed statistical analysis of these observations because of uncertainty about the appropriate theory. It is evident from simple statistical considerations, however, that vitamin C significantly decreases the number of malignant lesions in the mice in a group.

The degree of protection by vitamin C of hairless mice against skin cancer caused by ultraviolet irradiation is indicated by Figure 1, in which the fraction of mice that had developed lesions 4 mm or more in diameter (mostly malignant) by the final reading is shown in relation to the amount of vitamin C added to the chow. The results of both Experiment II and Experiment III are shown; although these experiments were carried out in different years, with two different batches of mice, the other conditions were essentially the same, and the results seem to be comparable without a change in scale.

It is seen that 9.2% of added ascorbic acid is indicated to provide about 85% protection. This amount of protection might be interpreted as resulting from a delay in the incidence of the malignant lesions by about two months.

The point at 19.2% vitamin C lies higher than that at 9.6%. Half of the vitamin C for the 19.2% group was sodium ascorbate, whereas only ascorbic acid was added for all the other groups; accordingly this point might well be omitted from the analysis. There is, for example, the possibility for the 19.2% group of a toxic effect of the large

amount of sodium ion in the food. If the 19.2% point were to be omitted the statistical significance would be slightly less for Experiment III.

The curve shown in Figure 1 has been drawn only to guide the eye. It suggests, however, that a somewhat greater protective effect might have been obtained with about 13% of ascorbic acid added to the chow.

Experiment A

In experiment II it was observed that the fractions of mice in group IIa (0% C) that developed lesions were rather consistently smaller than those for IIb (0.3% C) and IIc (0.6% C), whereas small differences in the opposite direction (-3% and -6%, respectively) might be expected (Fig. 1). We surmised that this observation resulted from statistical fluctuations, but it seemed worth while to make an additional experiment to check the effect of 0.3% of added vitamin C to the standard diet. This experiment was carried out in 1980. Because of added experience and some practical considerations (the need to complete the study before the laboratory was moved to another building in December 1980), the conditions of the study differed slightly from those of the earlier experiments. Nine readings were made for each of the two groups (Aa, no added vitamin, and Ab, 0.3% added vitamin C), beginning 24 days before the

Fig. 1: The fraction of mice that by the 10th reading had developed lesions 4 mm or more in diameter in relation to the amount of vitamin C added to the Lab-Blox chow. The points are for Experiment II (open circles) and Experiment III (filled circles). The curve shown has no significance other than to guide the eye.

cessation of irradiation and thereafter every 14 days. There were initially 45 mice in Aa and 39 in Ab. None of the mice died during the experiment. The small lesions that appeared to be actinic keratoses (not malignant) were not counted in Experiment A; they comprise about 45% of lesions less than 2 mm in diameter and less than 20% of those 2 to 4 mm in diameter in the other experiments.

The analysis of the observed numbers of mice with lesions of different sizes is given in Table IX. It is seen that, as expected, the difference between the two groups is not large. There are, however, twice as many negative values of the trend sum as positive values, indicating that the amount 0.3% of added ascorbic acid has some protective effect and that the opposite indication of Experiment II can be attributed to statistical fluctuation.

Experiment III; Vitamin E

In Tables V and VIII there are given the observations on groups IIa (the control group), IIg, IIh, IIi, IIj, and IIk, fed with chow containing 0 to 0.20% of vitamin E (*D,L*- α -tocopheryl acetate, Table I). The results of the application of the IARC statistical treatment to the observations in Table V are also given in that table.

It may first be noted that 23 of the values of the trend statistic T are positive (increasing numbers with malignancies) and 19 are negative, suggesting that an increase in the amount of vitamin E in the food neither increases nor decreases the fraction of mice with malignant lesions. The values of P for negative values of the trend sum range from 0.15 to 0.50, and hence give no support to any claim that vitamin E protects hairless mice against skin cancer. Of the readings with positive trend sum there are seven with low values of P : 0.001, 0.006, and 0.04 for readings 1, 2, and 3 of the any-lesion case, 0.03, 0.004, 0.05, and 0.04 for readings 1, 2, 3, and 10 of the case with lesions 2 mm or more in diameter, and 0.02, 0.03, and 0.002 for readings 1, 2, and 3 of the case with lesions 4 mm or more in diameter. In these cases many of the lesions are non-malignant. There is accordingly a suggestion that vitamin E favors the development of the small non-malignant lesions to some extent. We conclude that our studies of vitamin E taken with food indicate that it has little effect on the incidence of malignant skin lesions in hairless mice.

The weight of the mice

The weight of a mouse that has developed large tumors is determined in part by the progress of the disease. We wished to answer the question of whether the amounts of vitamin C and of vitamin E added to Wayne Lab-Blox had a deleterious effect on the health of the mice. Since the growth of the mice might be restricted by poor health and the mice should have reached maturity at the time that the measurements recorded in

the tables were made, the mean values of the weights of the mice without large lesions, 4 mm or more in diameter, at these times were calculated.

The mean weight of the mice at the first reading was 24.4 g, and the mean rate of increase was then 0.9 g per week, the large value reflecting their young age. The mean rate of increase during the next 32 weeks was 0.2 g per week, with most of the increase in the first four or five months and little change thereafter.

Although, as mentioned above, we surmised that the presence of large lesions might significantly affect the weight of the mice, it was observed that this effect is not large, the mean for the mice with large lesions in a group usually being within 1 g of that for the mice without large lesions in the same group. The weight of the tumors may be largely compensated for by the decreased weight of other tissues (emaciation) caused by the lesions.

Values of the mean weights at the 10th reading are shown in Figure 2. The linear regression equation for the vitamin C groups, both experiments (omitting the 19.2% group), is

$$W=30.49 \pm 0.18+(0.036+0.059) C$$

and that for the vitamin E groups is

$$W=31.25 \pm 0.19+(0.050 \pm 0.028) E$$

in which *C* and *E* are the percentage of vitamin C or vitamin E added to the chow. Thus there is indication of a small increase in mean weight with increased intake of either vitamin C or vitamin E, but in neither case is it statistically significant ($P=0.56$ for vitamin C, 0.14 for vitamin E).

Fig. 2: Mean weights of mice without lesions 4 mm or more in diameter in groups receiving vitamin C or vitamin E and control groups.

Conclusion

There is little doubt from these studies that change in the Wayne diet by addition of vitamin C is associated with change in the number of malignant lesions incurred by hairless mice exposed to ultraviolet light. The effect reported by BLACK with his mixture of four antioxidants may be caused in part by the vitamin C in the mixture.

The significance of these results with respect to the use of vitamin C for the prevention and treatment of human cancer is uncertain; qualitatively it may be said that the results support the thesis that vitamin C has value for human beings by providing protection against cancer, especially skin cancer caused by sunlight. Transfer of the results from the mouse to human beings is uncertain because the mouse synthesizes ascorbic acid in amounts of about 0.3 g per kg body weight per day, whereas human beings do not synthesize this substance. Moreover, there may be a homeostatic mechanism that decreases the amount synthesized by the mouse as the exogenous supply of ascorbate is increased.

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Tab. I: Composition of diets

- Ia, Ila, IIIa—Chow: Wayne Lab Blox, blended with 6.88% deionized water and repelleted.
- Ib (1.2% C), IIb (0.3% C), IIc (0.6% C), IId (1.2% C), IIe (2.4% C), IIIf (4.8% C), IIIIf (4.8% C).
IIIb (4.8% C), IIIc (9.6% C)—Chow+C: Wayne Lab Blox blended with 6.88% deionized water (5% for IIIc) and the indicated amount of L-ascorbic acid and repelleted.
- IIId (19.2% C)—Wayne Lab Blox blended with 3.71% deionized water, 9.49% L-ascorbic acid, and 10.80% sodium L-ascorbate and repelleted.
- Ic (0.05% E), IIg (0.0125% E), IIh (0.025% E), IIi (0.05% E), IIj (0.10% E), IIk (0.20% E)—Chow+E: Wayne Lab Blox blended with 6.88% deionized water and the indicated amount of D, L- α -tocopheryl acetate and repelleted.
- Id—Chow and antioxidants: Wayne Lab Blox blended with 6.88% deionized water, 1.2% L-ascorbic acid, 0.5% butylated hydroxytoluene, 0.05% D, L- α -tocopheryl acetate, and 0.1% glutathione and repelleted.

Tab. II: Distribution of lesions among actinic keratoses, papillomas, and cancers by inspection

Diameter of lesion	0 to 1.9 mm		2 to 3.9 mm		4 to 5.9 mm		6 to 9.9 mm		10 mm or more	
	8th	10th	8th	10th	8th	10th	8th	10th	8th	10th
Controls (IIa, IIIa)										
Total	763	1092	123	207	25	53	15	24	8	27
Actinic keratoses	442	535	34	40	2	2	0	0	0	0
Papillomas	321	556	87	151	6	22	1	5	0	0
Cancers	0	1	2	16	17	19	14	19	8	27
Vitamin C (IIb to III)										
Total	956	1620	224	349	53	75	19	47	14	42
Actinic keratoses	453	449	59	48	4	3	1	1	0	0
Papillomas	502	1120	154	275	32	34	4	6	0	0
Cancers	1	1	11	26	17	38	14	40	14	42
Vitamin C (IIIb to IIIId)										
Total	598	915	108	170	19	57	9	17	3	22
Actinic keratoses	364	563	11	23	1	0	0	0	0	0
Papillomas	234	352	95	140	3	21	0	0	0	0
Cancers	0	0	2	7	15	36	9	17	3	22
Vitamin E (IIg to IIk)										
Total	1073	1867	236	459	48	86	20	40	19	57
Actinic keratoses	551	532	73	85	4	3	1	1	0	0
Papillomas	521	1335	158	335	31	45	0	3	0	0
Cancers	1	0	5	39	13	38	19	36	19	57

Tab. III: Development of lesions of various sizes in mice in Experiment II: Wayne Lab-Blox plus 0, 0.3, 0.6, 1.2, 2.4, and 4.8% of vitamin C.

Reading:	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Diet/dose	Number of mice with any lesions									
IIa/.0										
New observations	1	9	8	16	8	4	7	1	0	2
Number at risk	59	58	49	40	24	16	12	5	4	4
Total live	59	59	59	58	58	58	58	58	57	55
IIf/.3										
New observations	2	12	8	9	5	5	3	0	1	0
Number at risk	45	43	31	23	14	9	4	1	1	0
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	40
IIc/.6										
New observations	0	0	16	7	5	4	4	2	1	0
Number at risk	45	45	42	26	19	14	9	5	3	2
Total live	45	45	42	42	42	42	41	41	40	40
IIId/1.2										
New observations	2	8	13	3	2	0	5	5	4	2
Number at risk	45	43	35	22	19	17	17	12	7	3
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	43

Tab. III, continued

Diet/dose	Number of mice with any lesions									
Ile/2.4										
New observations	1	6	8	13	7	3	1	2	1	1
Number at risk	45	44	38	29	16	9	6	5	3	2
Total live	45	45	45	44	44	44	44	44	44	43
Ilf/4.8										
New observations	1	3	5	10	7	4	4	2	4	2
Number at risk	45	44	41	36	26	19	15	10	8	4
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	43
Trend, T	-.12	-14.01	-18.78	-6.30	-.79	-4.06	-12.30	-2.94	3.57	.96
Trend sum, T*	-.12	-14.13	-32.91	-39.20	-39.99	-44.05	-56.35	-59.29	-55.72	-54.76
Z*	.03	1.36	2.16	2.08	1.92	2.	2.44	2.51	2.31	2.24
P (1)	.5	.09	.015	.02	.03	.025	.007	.006	.01	.015
2 mm lesions or larger										
Ila/.0										
New observations	0	0	3	10	4	10	6	5	3	4
Number at risk	59	59	59	55	45	41	31	25	20	17
Total live	59	59	59	58	58	58	58	58	57	55
Ilb/.3										
New observations	1	2	3	4	6	10	8	1	1	2
Number at risk	45	44	42	39	35	29	19	11	9	8
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	40
Ilc/.6										
New observations	0	0	3	3	6	7	3	2	3	4
Number at risk	45	45	42	39	36	30	22	19	17	14
Total live	45	45	42	42	42	42	41	41	40	40
Ild/1.2										
New observations	0	0	3	3	4	10	4	2	2	6
Number at risk	45	45	45	42	39	35	25	21	19	17
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	43
Ile/2.4										
New observations	0	0	2	6	7	4	3	5	5	5
Number at risk	45	45	45	42	36	29	25	22	17	12
Total live	45	45	45	44	44	44	44	44	44	43
Ilf/4.8										
New observations	0	1	2	1	2	3	5	3	4	6
Number at risk	45	45	44	42	41	39	36	30	27	23
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	43
Trend, T	-1.17	.97	-3.04	-14.64	-8.66	-27.35	-11.50	-2.99	1.67	.44
Trend sum, T*	-1.17	-.21	-3.25	-17.88	-26.55	-53.90	-65.40	-68.39	-66.72	-66.28
Z*	.72	.06	.45	1.65	1.93	3.14	3.39	3.33	3.07	2.86
P (1)	.25	.5	.3	.05	.025	.001	.0005	.0005	.001	.002
4 mm lesions or larger										
Ila/.0										
New observations	0	0	0	3	7	4	1	7	3	5
Number at risk	59	59	59	58	55	48	44	43	36	33
Total live	59	59	59	58	58	58	58	58	57	55

Tab. III, continued

Diet/dose	4 mm lesions or larger									
IIb/.3										
New observations	0	0	1	3	3	5	5	5	5	5
Number at risk	45	45	45	44	41	38	33	28	22	17
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	40
IIc/.6										
New observations	0	0	1	2	2	2	3	6	2	4
Number at risk	45	45	42	41	39	37	34	31	24	21
Total live	45	45	42	42	42	42	41	41	40	40
IIId/1.2										
New observations	0	0	1	2	1	2	3	4	7	4
Number at risk	45	45	45	44	42	41	39	36	32	25
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	43
IIe/2.4										
New observations	0	0	0	1	2	3	2	5	2	5
Number at risk	45	45	45	44	43	41	38	36	31	29
Total live	45	45	45	44	44	44	44	44	44	43
IIIf/4.8										
New observations	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	3	7
Number at risk	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	42	40	37
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	43
Trend, T	.00	.00	-2.35	-9.53	-14.84	-13.12	-5.09	-16.59	-8.44	-.31
Trend sum, T*	.00	.00	-2.35	-11.88	-26.72	-39.84	-44.93	-61.52	-69.96	-70.28
Z*	0.	0.	.83	1.95	3.05	3.64	3.5	3.97	4.03	3.6
P (1)	0.	0.	.2	.025	.001	.0001	.0001	.00005	.00005	.0001

Diet/dose	6 mm lesions or larger									
IIa/0										
New observations	0	0	0	0	2	4	0	5	4	4
Number at risk	59	59	59	58	58	56	52	52	47	42
Total live	59	59	59	58	58	58	58	58	57	55
IIb/.3										
New observations	0	0	0	0	4	1	5	0	3	7
Number at risk	45	45	45	45	45	41	40	35	34	31
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	40
IIc/.6										
New observations	0	0	0	0	1	1	3	1	6	7
Number at risk	45	45	42	42	42	41	39	36	34	27
Total live	45	45	42	42	42	42	41	41	40	40
IIId/1.2										
New observations	0	0	0	0	0	1	4	2	3	9
Number at risk	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	40	38	35
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	43
IIe/2.4										
New observations	0	0	0	0	1	4	0	1	3	3
Number at risk	45	45	45	44	44	43	39	39	38	35
Total live	45	45	45	44	44	44	44	44	44	43

Tab. III, continued

Diet/dose	6 mm lesions or larger									
IIf/4.8										
New observations	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	7
Number at risk	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	43	42
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	43
Trend, T	.00	.00	.00	.00	-7.68	-4.95	-10.33	-5.45	-11.85	-3.73
Trend sum, T*	.00	.00	.00	.00	-7.68	-12.63	-22.96	-28.40	-40.25	-43.98
Z*	0.	0.	0.	0.	1.67	1.78	2.52	2.7	3.14	2.74
P (1)	0.	0.	0.	0.	.05	.04	.006	.003	.001	.003
Diet/dose	10 mm lesions or larger									
IIf/0										
New observations	0	0	0	0	0	3	2	1	3	4
Number at risk	59	59	59	58	58	58	55	53	52	48
Total live	59	59	59	58	58	58	58	58	57	55
IIf/.3										
New observations	0	0	0	0	2	0	3	1	0	5
Number at risk	45	45	45	45	45	43	43	40	38	37
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	40
IIf/.6										
New observations	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	1	0	8
Number at risk	45	45	42	42	42	41	40	38	36	35
Total live	45	45	42	42	42	42	41	41	40	40
IIf/1.2										
New observations	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	4	3	4
Number at risk	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	40	36
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	43
IIf/2.4										
New observations	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	2
Number at risk	45	45	45	44	44	44	44	44	44	40
Total live	45	45	45	44	44	44	44	44	44	43
IIf/4.8										
New observations	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1
Number at risk	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	42
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	43
Trend, T	.00	.00	.00	.00	-3.25	-4.79	-8.52	-5.06	3.17	-16.90
Trend sum, T*	.00	.00	.00	.00	-3.25	-8.04	-16.57	-21.63	-18.46	-35.36
Z*	0.	0.	0.	0.	1.14	1.85	2.69	2.87	1.98	2.9
P (1)	0.	0.	0.	0.	.15	.03	.004	.002	.025	.002

* New observations are the number of mice at risk (that have not yet developed lesions of the indicated size) that develop such a lesion during the 14-day period.

Tab. IV: Development of lesions of various sizes in mice in Experiment III: Wayne Lab-Blox plus 0, 4.8, 9.6, and 19% if vitamin C

Reading:	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Diet/dose	Number of mice with any lesions									
IIIa/0										
New observations	0	1	20	14	11	6	5	1	1	0
Number at risk	60	60	59	39	25	14	8	3	2	1
Total live	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	59
IIIb/4.8										
New observations	0	1	11	12	9	4	6	0	0	1
Number at risk	45	45	44	33	21	12	8	2	2	2
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	44	43
IIIc/9.6										
New observations	0	0	5	10	11	6	7	4	0	1
Number at risk	45	45	45	40	30	19	13	6	2	2
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45
IIId/19.2										
New observations	0	0	8	2	5	7	9	4	4	1
Number at risk	45	45	41	33	31	26	19	10	6	2
Total live	45	45	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41
Trend, T	.00	-10.71	-78.60	-116.19	-86.27	-28.26	-28.20	4.11	16.80	4.80
Trend sum, T*	.00	-10.71	-89.31	-205.50	-291.77	-320.03	-348.23	-344.11	-327.31	-322.51
Z*	0.	1.06	2.11	3.65	4.38	4.39	4.51	4.36	4.08	3.99
P (1)	0.	.15	.02	.0001	.00005	.00005	.00005	.00005	.00005	.00005
2 mm lesions or larger										
IIIa/0										
New observations	0	0	3	4	5	6	8	9	2	7
Number at risk	60	60	60	57	53	48	42	34	25	23
Total live	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	59
IIIb/4.8										
New observations	0	0	1	4	1	3	7	7	2	5
Number at risk	45	45	45	44	40	39	35	28	21	19
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	44	43
IIIc/9.6										
New observations	0	0	0	1	1	0	4	2	2	9
Number at risk	45	45	45	45	44	43	43	39	37	35
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45
IIId/19.2										
New observations	0	0	0	1	2	0	2	3	4	9
Number at risk	45	45	41	41	40	38	38	36	33	29
Total live	45	45	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41
Trend, T	.00	.00	-25.26	-28.49	-17.49	-56.83	-63.77	-73.54	11.67	4.71
Trend sum, T*	.00	.00	-25.26	-53.75	-71.24	-128.07	-191.84	-265.38	-253.71	-249.00
Z*	0.	0.	1.8	2.07	2.14	3.27	3.88	4.58	4.1	3.56
P (1)	0.	0.	.04	.02	.015	.0005	.00005	.00005	.00005	.0001

Tab. IV, continued

Diet/dose	4 mm lesions or larger									
IIIa/0										
New observations	0	0	1	1	1	3	8	6	6	8
Number at risk	60	60	60	59	58	57	54	46	40	34
Total live	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	59
IIIb/4.8										
New observations	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	6	4	5
Number at risk	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	42	36	32
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	44	43
IIIc/9.6										
New observations	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	2
Number at risk	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	43	42
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45
IIId/19.2										
New observations	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	5
Number at risk	45	45	41	41	41	41	41	41	40	38
Total live	45	45	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41
Trend, T	.00	.00	-7.51	-7.55	-7.59	-22.90	-68.14	-55.28	-43.47	-37.02
Trend sum, T*	.00	.00	-7.51	-15.07	-22.66	-45.56	-113.70	-168.99	-212.46	-249.48
Z*	0.	0.	1.06	1.51	1.85	2.64	4.1	4.43	4.68	4.61
P (1)	0.	0.	.15	.07	.03	.004	.00005	.00005	.00005	.00005

Diet/dose	6 mm lesions or larger									
IIIa/0										
New observations	0	0	0	1	0	1	2	5	7	8
Number at risk	60	60	60	60	59	59	58	56	51	44
Total live	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	59
IIIb/4.8										
New observations	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	2
Number at risk	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	44	40
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	44	43
IIIc/9.6										
New observations	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
Number at risk	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45
IIId/19.2										
New observations	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	3
Number at risk	45	45	41	41	41	41	41	41	40	40
Total live	45	45	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41
Trend, T	.00	.00	.00	-7.51	.00	-7.55	-15.22	-26.94	-67.04	-34.42
Trend sum, T*	.00	.00	.00	-7.51	-7.51	-15.07	-30.28	-57.23	-124.27	-158.69
Z*	0.	0.	0.	1.06	1.06	1.51	2.15	2.59	3.93	3.78
P (1)	0.	0.	0.	.15	.15	.07	.015	.005	.00005	.00005

Tab. IV, continued

Diet/dose	10 mm lesions or larger									
IIIa/0										
New observations	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	7	6
Number at risk	60	60	60	60	60	59	59	59	58	51
Total live	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	59
IIIb/4.8										
New observations	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
Number at risk	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	44	43
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	44	43
IIIc/9.6										
New observations	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Number at risk	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45
IIId/19.2										
New observations	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2
Number at risk	45	45	41	41	41	41	41	41	40	40
Total live	45	45	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41
Trend, T	.00	.00	.00	.00	-7.51	.00	.00	4.06	-52.83	-30.14
Trend sum, T*	.00	.00	.00	.00	-7.51	-7.51	-7.51	-3.45	-56.28	-86.42
Z*	0.	0.	0.	0.	1.06	1.06	1.06	.28	.256	2.63
P (1)	0.	0.	0.	0.	.15	.15	.15	.4	.005	.004

Tab. V: Development of lesions of various sizes in mice in Experiment III: Wayne Lab-Blox plus 0, 0.0125, 0.025, 0.05, 0.10, and 0.20% of vitamin E.

Reading:	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Diet/dose	Number of mice with any lesions									
IIa/0										
New observations	1	9	8	16	8	4	7	1	0	2
Number at risk	59	58	49	40	24	16	12	5	4	4
Total live	59	59	59	58	58	58	58	58	57	55
IIg/0.13										
New observations	0	8	11	4	3	7	5	1	1	0
Number at risk	44	44	36	24	20	17	10	5	4	3
Total live	44	44	44	43	43	43	42	42	42	40
IIh/0.025										
New observations	3	14	6	5	5	5	1	4	0	0
Number at risk	45	42	28	22	17	12	7	6	2	1
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	43
III/.05										
New observations	5	14	5	3	3	6	6	1	0	0
Number at risk	44	39	25	20	17	14	7	1	0	0
Total live	44	44	44	44	44	44	43	43	43	41
IIj/.1										
New observations	5	5	11	5	6	3	6	2	2	0
Number at risk	45	40	35	24	19	13	10	4	2	0
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	43	43	43

Tab. V, continued

Diet/dose	Number of mice with any lesions									
IIk/.2										
New observations	7	12	3	7	1	7	5	0	1	0
Number at risk	45	38	26	23	16	15	7	2	2	1
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	44	41
Trend, T	.93	.45	-.22	-.09	-.41	.19	.26	-.05	.21	-.06
Trend sum, T*	.93	1.38	1.16	1.07	.66	.85	1.11	1.05	1.27	1.21
Z*	3.07	2.5	1.73	1.4	.8	.96	1.21	1.14	1.36	1.29
P (1)	.001	.006	.04	.08	.2	.15	.1	.15	.09	.1
Diet/dose										
2 mm lesions or larger										
IIa/.0										
New observations	0	0	3	10	4	10	6	5	3	4
Number at risk	59	59	59	55	45	41	31	25	20	17
Total live	59	59	59	58	58	58	58	58	57	55
IIg/.013										
New observations	0	0	3	5	3	3	5	3	2	3
Number at risk	44	44	44	40	35	32	29	24	21	18
Total live	44	44	44	43	43	43	42	42	42	40
IIh/.025										
New observations	0	2	5	4	3	8	4	3	3	3
Number at risk	45	45	43	38	34	31	23	19	16	12
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	43
IIi/.05										
New observations	0	1	5	4	3	8	3	3	7	3
Number at risk	44	44	43	38	34	31	22	19	16	9
Total live	44	44	44	44	44	44	43	43	43	41
IIj/.1										
New observations	2	0	1	3	3	6	5	7	3	6
Number at risk	45	43	43	42	39	36	30	24	17	16
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	43	43	43
IIk/.2										
New observations	1	3	4	4	3	7	4	6	3	4
Number at risk	45	44	41	37	33	30	22	18	12	9
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	44	41
Trend, T	.21	.33	.06	-.33	-.00	.06	-.01	.54	.20	.45
Trend sum, T*	.21	.55	.61	-.28	-.28	.34	.33	.87	1.07	1.52
Z*	1.82	2.7	1.69	.56	.48	.49	.43	1.06	1.25	1.7
P (1)	.03	.004	.05	.3	.3	.3	.3	.15	.1	.04
Diet/dose										
4 mm lesions or larger										
IIa/.0										
New observations	0	0	0	3	7	4	1	7	3	5
Number at risk	59	59	59	58	55	48	44	43	36	33
Total live	59	59	59	58	58	58	58	58	57	55
IIg/.013										
New observations	0	0	0	2	2	2	2	3	1	8
Number at risk	44	44	44	43	41	39	36	34	31	29
Total live	44	44	44	43	43	43	42	42	42	40

Tab. V, continued

Diet/dose	4 mm lesions or larger									
Iih/.025										
New observations	0	0	0	2	1	9	2	2	2	8
Number at risk	45	45	45	45	43	42	33	31	29	26
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	43
Iii/.05										
New observations	0	0	1	0	5	2	1	5	5	4
Number at risk	44	44	44	43	43	38	35	34	29	24
Total live	44	44	44	44	44	44	43	43	43	41
Iij/.1										
New observations	0	2	0	2	2	2	4	1	4	5
Number at risk	45	45	43	43	41	39	37	32	31	27
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	43	43	43
Iik/.2										
New observations	1	0	2	1	1	5	5	2	2	4
Number at risk	45	44	44	42	41	40	34	29	27	24
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	44	41
Trend, T	.14	.08	.27	-.13	-.39	.05	.60	-.34	.08	-.22
Trend sum, T*	.14	.22	.48	.36	-.04	.01	.61	.28	.36	.14
Z*	2.02	1.83	2.9	1.32	.1	.03	1.09	.44	.53	.18
P (1)	.02	.03	.002	.09	.5	.5	.15	.3	.3	.4
Diet/dose	6 mm lesions or larger									
Iia/.0										
New observations	0	0	0	0	2	4	0	5	4	4
Number at risk	59	59	59	58	58	56	52	52	47	42
Total live	59	59	59	58	58	58	58	58	57	55
Iig/.013										
New observations	0	0	0	2	0	0	1	2	0	8
Number at risk	44	44	44	43	41	41	40	39	37	36
Total live	44	44	44	43	43	43	42	42	42	40
Iih/.025										
New observations	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	4	2	7
Number at risk	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	42	38	34
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	43
Iii/.05										
New observations	0	0	0	1	1	1	2	3	1	5
Number at risk	44	44	44	44	43	42	40	38	35	34
Total live	44	44	44	44	44	44	43	43	43	41
Iij/.1										
New observations	0	0	0	0	2	2	2	0	1	5
Number at risk	45	45	45	45	45	43	41	37	37	36
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	43	43	43
Iik/.2										
New observations	0	0	0	0	0	4	2	3	2	4
Number at risk	45	45	45	45	45	45	40	38	35	32
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	44	41
Trend, T	.00	.00	.00	-.11	-.10	.36	.21	-.14	-.01	-.18
Trend sum, T*	.00	.00	.00	-.11	-.21	.15	.36	.22	.21	.03
Z*	0.	0.	0.	.93	1.03	.49	.99	.48	.42	.05
P (1)	0.	0.	0.	.2	.15	.3	.15	.3	.3	.5

Tab. V, continued

Diet/dose	10 mm lesions or larger									
Ila/.0										
New observations	0	0	0	0	0	3	2	1	3	4
Number at risk	59	59	59	58	58	58	55	53	52	48
Total live	59	59	59	58	58	58	58	58	57	55
Ilg/.013										
New observations	0	0	0	0	2	0	1	1	0	5
Number at risk	44	44	44	43	43	41	40	39	38	37
Total live	44	44	44	43	43	43	42	42	42	40
Iih/.025										
New observations	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	3	5
Number at risk	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	41	36
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	43
Iii/.05										
New observations	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	6
Number at risk	44	44	44	44	44	43	41	40	40	39
Total live	44	44	44	44	44	44	43	43	43	41
Iij/.1										
New observations	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	1	4
Number at risk	45	45	45	45	45	45	43	40	40	39
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	43	43	43
Iik/.2										
New observations	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	4	5
Number at risk	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	42	41	35
Total live	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	44	41
Trend, T	.00	.00	.00	.00	-.11	-.12	.09	-.08	.28	.13
Trend sum, T*	.00	.00	.00	.00	-.11	-.24	-.15	-.23	.04	.17
Z*	0.	0.	0.	0.	.93	1.15	.53	.71	.11	.32
P (1)	0.	0.	0.	0.	.2	.15	.3	.25	.5	.4

Tab. VI: Number of lesions in various ranges of diameter and number of mice with those lesions: Experiment II, vitamin C.

Reading:	Number of lesions of up to 1.9 mm / Number of mice with those lesions									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Ila/.0										
Total mice	2/1	17/10	25/14	61/29	72/32	124/39	182/49	268/51	346/48	412/51
	59	59	59	58	58	58	58	58	57	55
Iib/.3										
Total mice	1/1	20/12	40/19	88/27	113/31	131/33	174/38	225/38	320/40	368/38
	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	40
Iic/.6										
Total mice	0/0	0/0	28/14	59/21	92/26	118/28	176/36	192/34	283/38	339/37
	45	45	42	42	42	42	41	41	40	40
Iid/1.2										
Total mice	2/2	17/10	43/22	71/21	88/24	88/19	159/31	199/35	266/40	316/40
	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	43
Iie/2.4										
Total mice	1/1	8/7	27/15	62/25	80/29	109/30	151/32	184/38	259/39	331/41
	45	45	45	44	44	44	44	44	44	43
Iif/4.8										
Total mice	1/1	4/3	10/7	30/18	56/24	70/23	105/27	156/34	206/38	265/38
	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	43

Tab. VI, continued

Number of lesions 2 to 3.9 mm / Number of mice with those lesions										
IIa/.0	0/0	0/0	3/3	15/11	13/9	33/19	40/25	57/28	64/28	102/36
Total mice	59	59	59	58	58	58	58	58	57	55
IIb/.3	1/1	2/2	7/4	10/7	17/13	40/22	56/23	66/25	58/25	75/24
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	40
IIc/.6	0/0	0/0	2/2	4/3	14/10	35/19	43/18	43/20	44/21	83/24
Total mice	45	45	42	42	42	42	41	41	40	40
IId/1.2	0/0	0/0	3/3	11/6	11/8	37/20	38/22	48/21	44/21	60/26
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	43
IIe/2.4	0/0	0/0	2/2	5/5	11/11	22/16	40/18	44/23	46/23	71/31
Total mice	45	45	45	44	44	44	44	44	44	43
IIf/4.8	0/0	1/1	2/2	4/3	3/3	10/9	19/11	23/11	33/17	60/23
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	43

Number of lesions 4 to 5.9 mm / Number of mice with those lesions										
IIa/.0	0/0	0/0	0/0	3/3	9/8	9/7	7/6	12/9	20/15	20/16
Total mice	59	59	59	58	58	58	58	58	57	55
IIb/.3	0/0	0/0	1/1	4/3	5/3	11/7	19/11	22/11	15/12	23/15
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	40
IIc/.6	0/0	0/0	3/1	5/3	5/4	5/5	7/6	11/10	15/10	18/13
Total mice	45	45	42	42	42	42	41	41	40	40
IId/1.2	0/0	0/0	1/1	2/2	4/3	8/5	8/6	10/8	13/10	14/10
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	43
IIe/2.4	0/0	0/0	0/0	1/1	2/2	1/1	4/4	7/5	8/5	11/10
Total mice	45	45	45	44	44	44	44	44	44	43
IIf/4.8	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	3/2	3/3	4/4	9/7
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	43

Number of lesions 6 to 9.9 mm / Number of mice with those lesions										
IIa/.0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	2/2	4/4	1/1	6/6	4/4	11/10
Total mice	59	59	59	58	58	58	58	58	57	55
IIb/.3	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	4/4	4/4	5/5	7/6	16/10	9/8
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	40
IIc/.6	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	1/1	3/3	1/1	11/8	17/13
Total mice	45	45	42	42	42	42	41	41	40	40
IId/1.2	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	5/4	5/4	3/3	12/9
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	43
IIe/2.4	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	1/1	4/4	3/3	5/4	4/4	2/2
Total mice	45	45	45	44	44	44	44	44	44	43
IIf/4.8	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	1/1	0/0	7/6
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	43

Tab. VI, continued

	Number of lesions 10 mm and larger / Number of mice with those lesions									
IIa/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	3/3	6/5	6/6	8/8	12/11
Total mice	59	59	59	58	58	58	58	58	57	55
IIb/3	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	2/2	1/1	4/4	5/5	8/6	10/8
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	40
IIc/6	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	1/1	1/1	3/3	4/4	4/4	13/12
Total mice	45	45	42	42	42	42	41	41	40	40
IId/1.2	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	1/1	1/1	5/5	7/6	11/9
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	43
IIf/2.4	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	3/3	6/5
Total mice	45	45	45	44	44	44	44	44	44	43
IIg/4.8	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	2/2	2/2
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	43

Tab. VII: Number of lesions in various ranges of diameter and number of mice with those lesions: Experiment III, vitamin C.

Reading:	Number of lesions of up to 1.9 mm / Number of mice with those lesions									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
IIIa/0	0/0	1/1	33/19	73/32	168/41	265/50	364/56	495/57	638/59	680/58
Total mice	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	59
IIIb/4.8	0/0	1/1	24/11	55/22	92/28	115/32	244/42	308/40	402/42	419/42
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	44	43
IIIc/9.6	0/0	0/0	5/5	20/14	46/20	75/29	119/35	167/39	233/37	282/41
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45
IIId/19.2	0/0	0/0	12/8	15/7	24/12	53/18	83/28	123/33	148/37	214/38
Total mice	45	45	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41
Number of lesions 2 to 3.9 mm / Number of mice with those lesions										
IIIa/0	0/0	0/0	2/2	8/5	13/10	23/15	41/23	66/29	73/28	105/36
Total mice	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	59
IIIb/4.8	0/0	0/0	1/1	5/5	6/5	9/7	16/13	31/19	34/19	37/18
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	44	43
IIIc/9.6	0/0	0/0	0/0	1/1	2/2	1/1	6/5	8/5	7/5	26/15
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45
IIId/19.2	0/0	0/0	0/0	1/1	3/3	1/1	7/5	11/6	14/9	28/18
Total mice	45	45	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41

Tab. VII, continued

Number of lesions 4 to 5.9 mm / Number of mice with those lesions										
IIIa/.0	0/0	0/0	1/1	1/1	2/2	4/4	9/9	13/13	20/13	33/23
Total mice	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	59
IIIb/4.8	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	2/2	6/6	7/7	16/12
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	44	43
IIIc/9.6	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	2/2	3/3	3/2
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45
IIId/19.2	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	5/2	8/6
Total mice	45	45	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41

Number of lesions 6 to 9.9 mm / Number of mice with those lesions										
IIIa/.0	0/0	0/0	0/0	1/1	0/0	1/1	3/3	9/8	5/5	13/11
Total mice	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	59
IIIb/4.8	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	4/4	3/3
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	44	43
IIIc/9.6	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	2/2
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45
IIId/19.2	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	1/1
Total mice	45	45	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41

Number of lesions 10 mm and larger / Number of mice with those lesions										
IIIa/.0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	1/1	1/1	1/1	2/2	10/9	16/14
Total mice	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	59
IIIb/4.8	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	3/3
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	44	43
IIIc/9.6	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	2/2
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45
IIId/19.2	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	1/1	1/1	3/3
Total mice	45	45	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41

Tab. VIII: Number of lesions in various ranges of diameter and number of mice with those lesions: Experiment II, vitamin E.

Reading:	Number of lesions of up to 1.9 mm/Number of mice with those lesions									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Ila/.0	2/1	17/10	25/14	61/29	72/32	124/39	182/49	268/51	346/48	412/51
Total mice	59	59	59	58	58	58	58	58	57	55
Ilg/.013	0/0	11/8	39/18	61/19	74/19	109/28	168/31	224/32	292/36	343/35
Total mice	44	44	44	43	43	43	42	42	42	40
Iih/.025	4/3	29/17	54/22	64/24	93/28	117/30	198/32	232/41	350/42	350/40
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	43
Iii/.05	8/5	34/18	42/19	67/23	96/25	127/28	188/34	218/38	360/40	410/40
Total mice	44	44	44	44	44	44	43	43	43	41
Iij/.1	5/5	14/10	23/19	40/22	51/27	78/31	125/37	160/34	244/42	348/42
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	43	43	43
Iik/.2	7/6	24/17	44/20	64/26	95/25	150/33	211/39	239/40	354/43	416/39
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	44	41
Number of lesions 2 to 3.9 mm / Number of mice with those lesions										
Ila/.0	0/0	0/0	3/3	15/11	13/9	33/19	40/25	57/28	64/28	102/36
Total mice	59	59	59	58	58	58	58	58	57	55
Ilg/.013	0/0	0/0	3/3	7/5	9/6	28/11	48/16	43/18	47/21	68/20
Total mice	44	44	44	43	43	43	42	42	42	40
Iih/.025	0/0	2/2	7/6	12/10	18/11	37/19	46/21	49/23	70/29	83/31
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	43
Iii/.05	0/0	1/1	9/6	18/9	19/10	34/17	37/20	62/21	63/24	101/27
Total mice	44	44	44	44	44	44	43	43	43	41
Iij/.1	2/2	1/1	2/2	4/3	5/4	10/9	16/15	33/19	37/18	62/24
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	43	43	43
Iik/.2	0/0	4/4	7/6	12/10	20/11	28/16	41/21	49/26	70/31	145/34
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	44	41
Number of lesions 4 to 5.9 mm / Number of mice with those lesions										
Ila/.0	0/0	0/0	0/0	3/3	9/8	9/7	7/6	12/9	20/15	20/16
Total mice	59	59	59	58	58	58	58	58	57	55
Ilg/.013	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	3/2	5/4	8/4	11/7	10/8	13/11
Total mice	44	44	44	43	43	43	42	42	42	40
Iih/.025	0/0	0/0	0/0	2/2	1/1	15/10	18/13	17/12	18/11	22/15
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	43
Iii/.05	0/0	0/0	1/1	0/0	5/5	9/6	4/4	10/8	14/13	23/14
Total mice	44	44	44	44	44	44	43	43	43	41
Iij/.1	0/0	2/2	1/1	4/4	5/4	2/2	5/5	2/2	7/6	14/10
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	43	43	43
Iik/.2	1/1	0/0	2/2	3/3	5/3	10/6	12/9	8/8	13/9	14/8
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	44	41

Tab. VIII, continued

Number of lesions 6 to 9.9 mm / Number of mice with those lesions										
IIa/.0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	2/2	4/4	1/1	6/6	4/4	11/10
Total mice	59	59	59	58	58	58	58	58	57	55
IIg/.013	0/0	0/0	0/0	2/2	0/0	0/0	0/0	2/2	4/2	7/6
Total mice	44	44	44	43	43	43	42	42	42	40
IIh/.025	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	1/1	0/0	2/2	3/3	8/5	14/9
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	43
IIi/.05	0/0	0/0	0/0	1/1	1/1	2/2	4/3	6/5	5/5	9/8
Total mice	44	44	44	44	44	44	43	43	43	41
IIj/.1	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	2/2	2/1	3/3	3/3	4/3	4/3
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	43	43	43
IIk/.2	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	4/4	5/3	6/5	4/4	6/5
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	44	41

Number of lesions 10 mm and larger / Number of mice with those lesions

IIa/.0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	3/3	6/5	6/6	8/8	12/11
Total mice	59	59	59	58	58	58	58	58	57	55
IIg/.013	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	2/2	2/2	3/3	5/4	5/4	10/8
Total mice	44	44	44	43	43	43	42	42	42	40
IIh/.025	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	1/1	4/4	8/7	21/12
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	43
IIi/.05	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	2/1	2/2	4/3	3/3	6/4	11/8
Total mice	44	44	44	44	44	44	43	43	43	41
IIj/.1	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	2/2	3/3	4/3	6/4	12/8
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	43	43	43
IIk/.2	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	2/2	3/3	8/7	13/11
Total mice	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	44	41

Tab. IX: Development of lesions of various sizes in mice in Experiment A:
Wayne Lab-Blox plus 0.0 or 0.3% of vitamin C.

Reading:	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Diet/dose	Number of mice with any lesions								
<hr/>									
Aa/.0									
New observations	0	4	2	1	12	11	2	2	5
Number at risk	45	45	40	38	37	25	14	12	10
Total live	45	45	44	44	44	44	44	44	42
Ab/.3									
New observations	0	1	5	1	4	9	3	4	3
Number at risk	39	39	38	33	32	28	19	16	12
Total live	39	39	39	39	39	39	39	39	39
Trend, T	.00	-.40	.48	.02	-1.03	-.47	.04	.17	-.41
Trend sum, T*	.00	-.40	.08	.10	-.92	-1.39	-1.36	-1.19	-1.60
Z*	0.	1.21	.16	.19	1.22	1.5	1.39	1.15	1.47
P (1)	0.	.1	.4	.4	.1	.07	.08	.15	.07
<hr/>									
Diet/dose	2 mm lesions or larger								
<hr/>									
Aa/.0									
New observations	0	0	2	1	9	5	3	0	5
Number at risk	45	45	44	42	41	32	27	24	24
Total live	45	45	44	44	44	44	44	44	42
Ab/.3									
New observations	0	0	2	2	2	7	5	3	4
Number at risk	39	39	39	37	35	33	26	21	18
Total live	39	39	39	39	39	39	39	39	39
Trend, T	.00	.00	.04	.18	-.92	.27	.32	.48	.04
Trend sum, T*	.00	.00	.04	.21	-.71	-.43	-.11	.37	.41
Z*	0.	0.	.12	.55	1.17	.56	.13	.41	.42
P (1)	0.	0.	.5	.3	.1	.3	.4	.3	.5
<hr/>									
Diet/dose	4 mm lesions or larger								
<hr/>									
Aa/.0									
New observations	0	0	1	1	2	2	5	3	2
Number at risk	45	45	44	43	42	40	38	33	30
Total live	45	45	44	44	44	44	44	44	42
Ab/.3									
New observations	0	0	0	0	2	3	4	3	4
Number at risk	39	39	39	39	39	37	34	30	27
Total live	39	39	39	39	39	39	39	39	39
Trend, T	.00	.00	-.14	-.14	.02	.18	-.08	.04	.35
Trend sum, T*	.00	.00	-.14	-.28	-.26	-.08	-.16	-.11	.23
Z*	0.	0.	.94	1.34	.72	.17	.24	.16	.29
P (1)	0.	0.	.15	.09	.25	.4	.4	.4	.4

Tab. IX, continued

Diet/dose	6mm lesions or larger								
Aa/.0									
New observations	0	0	0	1	2	1	6	1	0
Number at risk	45	45	44	44	43	41	40	34	33
Total live	45	45	44	44	44	44	44	44	42
Ab/.3									
New observations	0	0	0	0	1	3	1	1	4
Number at risk	39	39	39	39	39	38	35	34	33
Total live	39	39	39	39	39	39	39	39	39
Trend, T	.00	.00	.00	-.14	-.13	.32	-.68	.00	.60
Trend sum, T*	.00	.00	.00	-.14	-.27	.05	-.63	-.63	-.03
Z*	0.	0.	0.	.94	.91	.13	1.11	1.04	.04
P (1)	0.	0.	0.	.15	.2	.4	.15	.15	.5
<hr/>									
Diet/dose	10 mm lesions or larger								
Aa/.0									
New observations	0	0	0	0	1	0	4	1	1
Number at risk	45	45	44	44	44	43	43	39	37
Total live	45	45	44	44	44	44	44	44	42
Ab/.3									
New observations	0	0	0	0	0	1	4	1	1
Number at risk	39	39	39	39	39	39	38	34	33
Total live	39	39	39	39	39	39	39	39	39
Trend, T	.00	.00	.00	.00	-.14	.16	.07	.02	.02
Trend sum, T*	.00	.00	.00	.00	-.14	.02	.09	.11	.13
Z*	0.	0.	0.	0.	.94	.08	.2	.22	.24
P (1)	0.	0.	0.	0.	.15	.5	.4	.4	.4

References

1. CAMERON, E., PAULING, L.: *Cancer and Vitamin C*. Linus Pauling Institute of Science and Medicine, Menlo Park, 1979.
2. CAMERON, E., BAIRD, G.: *IRCS*, August, 1973.
3. CAMERON, E., PAULING, L.: *Oncology* 27, 181-192 (1973).
4. CAMERON, E., PAULING, L.: *Chem-biol. Interactions* 9, 273-283 (1974).
5. CAMERON, E., CAMPBELL, A.: *Chem-biol. Interactions* 11, 285-315 (1974).
6. CAMERON, E., CAMPBELL, A., JACK, T.: *Chem-biol. Interactions* 11, 387-393 (1975).
7. CAMERON, E., PAULING, L.: *Proc. natn. Acad. Sci. USA* 73, 3685-3689 (1976).
8. CAMERON, E., PAULING, L.: *Proc. natn. Acad. Sci. USA* 75, 4538-4542 (1978).
9. CAMERON, E., PAULING, L.: *Proc. natn. Acad. Sci. USA* 75, 6252 (1978).
10. CAMERON, E., PAULING, L., LEIBOVITZ, B.: *Cancer Res.* 39, 663-681 (1979).
11. BLACK, H. S. and LO, W. B.: *Nature* 234, 306-308 (1971).
12. BLACK, H. S. and CHAN, J. T.: *J. Invest. Dermatol.* 65, 412-416 (1975).
13. BLACK, H. S. and DOUGLAS D. R.: *Cancer Res.* 33, 2094-2096 (1973).
14. PETO, R., PIKE, M. C., DAY, N. E., GRAY, R. G., LEE, P. N., PARISH, S., PETO, J., RICHARDS, S., and WAHRENDORF, J.: In: *IARC Monographs on the Evaluation of the Carcinogenic Risk of Chemicals to Humans; Supplement 2, Long-term and short-term screening assays for carcinogens: a critical appraisal*. International Agency for Research on Cancer, Lyon 1980.

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Contents

PAULING, L.: Introduction	7
<i>Vitamin C and Immunology</i>	
SIEGEL, B. V. and LEIBOVITZ, B.: The Multifactorial Role of Vitamin C in Health and Disease	9
ANDERSON, R.: Effects of Ascorbate on Normal and Abnormal Leucocyte Functions <i>In Vitro</i> and <i>In Vivo</i>	23
PANUSH, R. S., DELAFUENTE, J. C., KATZ, P. and JOHNSON, J.: Modulation of Certain Immunologic Responses by Vitamin C. III. Potentiation of <i>In Vitro</i> and <i>In Vivo</i> Lymphocyte Responses	35
BANIČ, S.: Immunostimulation by Vitamin C	49
<i>Vitamin C and Cancer</i>	
PAULING, L., WILLOUGHBY, R., REYNOLDS, R., BLAISDELL, B. E. and LAWSON, S.: Incidence of Squamous Cell Carcinoma in Hairless Mice Irradiated with Ultraviolet Light in Relation to Intake of Ascorbic Acid (Vitamin C) and of D, L- α -Tocopherol Acetate (Vitamin E)	53
BASU, T. K.: Vitamin C-Aspirin Interactions	83
SCHMÄHL, D. and EISENBRAND, G.: Influence of Ascorbic Acid on the Endogenous (Intragastral) Formation of N-Nitroso Compounds	91
MURATA, A., MORISHIGE, F. and YAMAGUCHI, H.: Prolongation of Survival Times of Terminal Cancer Patients by Administration of Large Doses of Ascorbate	103
CAMERON, E.: Vitamin C and Cancer: An Overview	115
<i>Vitamin C and Lipid Metabolism</i>	
GRECO, A. M. and LA ROCCA, L.: Correlation Between Chronic Hypovitaminosis C in Old Age and Haematic Levels of Cholesterol and Triglycerides	129

GINTER, E., BOBEK, P., KUBEC, F., VOZÁR, J. and URBANOVÁ, D.: Vitamin C in the Control of Hypercholesterolemia in Man	137
FIDANZA, A., AUDISIO, M. and MASTROIACOVO, P.: Vitamin C and Cholesterol	153
WILSON, C. W. M.: Appetite for Vitamin C: Its Relationship to Cellular Energy Potential	173
ODUMOSU, A.: How Vitamin C, Clofibrate and Diosgenin Control Cholesterol Metabolism in Male Guinea-Pigs	187
<i>Workshop: The Role of Vitamin C in Lipid Metabolism</i>	197
<i>Workshop: Vitamin C in Immunology and Cancer</i>	209
<i>Other Aspects on Vitamin C</i>	
HANCK, A.: Tolerance and Effects of High Doses of Ascorbic Acid	221
SHARMA, S. C.: Interactions of Ascorbic Acid with Prostaglandins	239
TEWFIK, F. A., TEWFIK, H. H. and RILEY, E. F.: The Influence of Ascorbic Acid on the Growth of Solid Tumors in Mice and on Tumor Control by X-Irradiation	257
TEWFIK, H. H., TEWFIK, F. A. and RILEY E. F.: The Influence of Ascorbic Acid on Survival of Mice Following Whole Body X-Irradiation	265
IRVIN, T. T.: Vitamin C Requirements in Postoperative Patients	277
BAINES, M.: Vitamin C and Exposure to Alcohol	287
List of Authors	294

Foreword

International Symposia on vitamin C in Brazil have almost become a tradition. After the extremely successful Symposia held in Rio de Janeiro in 1976 and 1978, a Third International Symposium on vitamin C was held in São Paulo from the 8th to the 10th September 1980 under the auspices of the Academia Brasileira de Medicina Militar and the Medical Faculty of the State University of São Paulo. The Symposium was chaired by Linus Pauling, Bras Itapaci Magalhães and Alfred Hanck.

Central topics were new findings on the role of vitamin C in immunology, in cancer and in lipid metabolism. Workshops produced fruitful discussions of new findings and current aspects, aiming at a better understanding of the role of vitamin C in health and disease. These may help in decision-making for further research and practical application of our present knowledge.

It is hoped that this book will reach as broad an audience as did these on previous Symposia, adding to the medical knowledge about vitamin C, not least for the benefit of the patients.

A. Hanck